

1 decimatoR: an R package to convert
2 heterogeneous coordinate formats into decimal
3 degrees

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16 Abstract

- 17 1. Spatial data syntheses are largely based on the integration of published
18 geographical information, such as the location of observations, experimental
19 fields or sampling sites. In addition, geographic coordinates can be used to
20 associate the attributed data to other geographic information, such as climatic
21 or land-use maps. Geographic coordinates are commonly reported either as
22 degrees-minutes-seconds or as decimal points or -for geographic ranges- as
23 coordinate intervals. Although there are known formulas to convert degrees into
24 decimals, these formats hinder the integration of large datasets from various
25 sources.
- 26 2. We here present `decimatoR`, an R package for handling datasets from
27 different sources and convert all coordinate formats into decimal points. We
28 demonstrate the functionality of `decimatoR` with an example of a dataset with
29 agricultural field experiment results.
- 30 3. `decimatoR` facilitates the homogenization of coordinate formats by providing
31 functions to transform degrees-minutes-seconds, degrees-decimal minutes
32 and coordinate intervals into decimal points. The functions can handle all
33 different kinds of symbols (°, ', ", ' , ") and allow the user to choose the preferred
34 segment of the geographical range interval.
- 35 4. The increasing demand for spatial data syntheses from the ecological
36 community makes `decimatoR` a powerful tool in the hands of ecologists and
37 facilitates the study of integrative research questions.

38

39 [Abstract in Russian]

- 40 1. В основе объединения географических данных лежит интеграция
41 опубликованной географической информации, такой как точки
42 наблюдения, экспериментальные площадки и точки пробоотбора.
43 Географические координаты могут быть использованы для привязки
44 атрибутированных данных к другим географическим источникам,
45 например, климатическим картам или картам землепользования. Обычно
46 координаты указываются в формате градусов-минут-секунд, десятичных
47 дробей или, в случае диапазонов, в виде координатных интервалов.
48 Несмотря на наличие формул для преобразования градусов в десятичные
49 числа, разнообразие используемых форматов координат затрудняет
50 слияние больших наборов данных из различных источников.
- 51 2. В связи с этим мы представляем `decimatoR` — пакет на языке R,
52 предназначенный для работы с данными из различных источников и
53 преобразования всех форматов координат в десятичные координаты. Мы
54 демонстрируем возможности `decimatoR` на примере
55 данных результатов сельскохозяйственных полевых экспериментов.
- 56 3. Этот пакет упрощает унификацию форматов координат, предлагая
57 функции для преобразования градусов-минут-секунд, градусов-
58 десятичных минут и координатных интервалов в десятичные значения.
59 Функции `decimatoR` поддерживают различные символы (°, ', ", ' , ") и
60 позволяют пользователю выбирать нужный сегмент интервала
61 географического диапазона.

62 4. С учетом растущего спроса на синтез пространственных данных со
63 стороны экологического сообщества, `decimatoR` становится мощным
64 инструментом для экологов и облегчает исследование интегративных
65 вопросов.

66

67 [Abstract in Greek]

- 68 1. Η σύνθεση χωρικών πληροφοριών βασίζεται κυρίως στην ενοποίηση
69 δημοσιευμένων γεωγραφικών δεδομένων, όπως οι τοποθεσίες όπου
70 πραγματοποιήθηκαν παρατηρήσεις ή πειράματα ή συλλογή δεδομένων. Οι
71 γεωγραφικές συντεταγμένες μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν, επιπλέον, για να
72 συσχετιστούν τα χωρικά δεδομένα με άλλες μεταβλητές, όπως κλιματικοί
73 χάρτες ή χάρτες χρήσεων γης. Οι γεωγραφικές συντεταγμένες συνήθως
74 αναφέρονται ως μοίρες-πρώτα λεπτά-δευτερόλεπτα ή ως δεκαδικά κλάσματα
75 ή ως διαστήματα. Παρότι υπάρχουν γνωστοί μαθηματικοί τύποι για τη
76 μετατροπή μοιρών σε δεκαδικά κλάσματα, η ποικιλία των τύπων
77 συντεταγμένων καθιστά δύσκολη τη συνένωση διαφόρων βάσεων δεδομένων
78 που περιέχουν διαφορετικές μορφές συντεταγμένων.
- 79 2. Το πακέτο `decimatoR`, γραμμένο στη γλώσσα προγραμματισμού R,
80 χρησιμεύει στην διαχείριση βάσεων δεδομένων από διαφορετικές πηγές και
81 στην μετατροπή όλων των πιθανών μορφών συντεταγμένων σε δεκαδικά
82 κλάσματα για περαιτέρω χρήση. Παρουσιάζουμε τη λειτουργία του πακέτου
83 `decimatoR` με τη χρήση ενός παραδείγματος μιας βάσης δεδομένων με
84 πειράματα παραγωγικότητας σε αγροτικά οικοσυστήματα.
- 85 3. Το πακέτο `decimatoR` διευκολύνει την ομογενοποίηση των διάφορων τύπων
86 γεωγραφικών συντεταγμένων με την παροχή εντολών για τη μετατροπή των
87 τύπων μοίρες-πρώτα λεπτά-δευτερόλεπτα, μοίρες-δεκαδικά λεπτά και
88 γεωγραφικά διαστήματα σε δεκαδικές συντεταγμένες. Οι εντολές μπορούν να
89 λειτουργήσουν με διάφορα σύμβολα (°, ', ", ' , ") και επιτρέπουν την επιλογή
90 συγκεκριμένων ορίων των διαστημάτων (κατώτερο ή ανώτερο όριο).
- 91 4. Η αυξανόμενη ανάγκη για σύνθεση χωρικών δεδομένων στην Οικολογία
92 καθιστά το `decimatoR` ένα σημαντικό εργαλείο στα χέρια των
93 περιβαλλοντολόγων και διευκολύνει την εξέταση διεπιστημονικών ερευνητικών
94 ερωτημάτων.

95

96 [Abstract in German]

- 97 1. Räumliche Datensynthesen beruhen weitgehend auf der Integration
98 veröffentlichter geografischer Informationen, z. B. der Lage von
99 Beobachtungen, Versuchsfeldern oder Probenahmestellen. Darüber hinaus
100 können geografische Koordinaten verwendet werden, um die zugeordneten
101 Daten mit anderen geografischen Informationen, wie Klima- oder
102 Landnutzungskarten, zu verknüpfen. Geographische Koordinaten werden
103 üblicherweise entweder als Grad-Minuten-Sekunden oder als Dezimalpunkte
104 oder - für geographische Bereiche - als Koordinatenintervalle angegeben.
105 Obwohl es bekannte Formeln zur Umrechnung von Grad in Dezimalzahlen gibt,
106 erschweren diese Formate die Integration großer Datensätze aus
107 verschiedenen Quellen.
- 108 2. Wir stellen hier `decimatoR` vor, ein R-Paket zur Verarbeitung von
109 Datensätzen aus verschiedenen Quellen und zur Umwandlung aller

110 Koordinatenformate in Dezimalpunkte. Wir demonstrieren die Funktionalität
111 von `decimatoR` am Beispiel eines Datensatzes mit landwirtschaftlichen
112 Feldversuchsergebnissen.

113 3. `decimatoR` erleichtert die Homogenisierung von Koordinatenformaten durch
114 die Bereitstellung von Funktionen zur Umwandlung von Grad-Minuten-
115 Sekunden, Grad-Dezimal-Minuten und Koordinatenintervallen in
116 Dezimalpunkte. Die Funktionen können alle Arten von Symbolen (°, ', ", ' , ")
117 verarbeiten und erlauben es dem Benutzer, das bevorzugte Segment des
118 geographischen Bereichsintervalls zu wählen.

119 4. Die zunehmende Nachfrage nach räumlichen Datensynthesen seitens der
120 ökologischen Gemeinschaft macht `decimatoR` zu einem mächtigen
121 Werkzeug in den Händen von Ökologen und erleichtert die Untersuchung
122 integrativer Forschungsfragen.

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148 INTRODUCTION

149 In recent years, researchers have recognized that ecological processes occur at defined
150 spatial and temporal scales, hence increasing the demand for better and wider sampling, in
151 order to be able to detect and quantify spatial patterns over a wide range of scales (Borcard
152 & Legendre, 2002). Similarly, the European Data Integration Group emphasizes that
153 visualizing data with high spatial and temporal resolution can reveal phenomena otherwise
154 invisible (Joubert - De Bellefon et al., 2018). The field of landscape ecology underscores the
155 importance of habitat composition and spatial configuration in ecological processes,
156 supporting biodiversity conservation, global change research, sustainable development, and
157 landscape planning (Yu et al., 2019).

158 The era of big data has transformed ecological research. Scientists are now encouraged to
159 collectively manage and analyze vast datasets while maintaining high-quality information
160 (Hampton et al., 2013). Ecology has evolved into an integrative discipline, transitioning from
161 small-scale, short-term studies to large-scale, multidisciplinary projects that leverage diverse
162 datasets through advanced analytical tools (Reichman et al., 2011). Modern ecological big-
163 data systems include *in situ* and remote sensors, biodiversity databases, citizen science
164 campaigns, and permanent monitoring stations. These systems rely on open code and data-
165 sharing platforms, flexible statistical models capable of handling heterogeneous data, and
166 cloud computing to enable high-volume analytics (Farley et al., 2018). The digitalization of
167 biological and paleontological collections has further revolutionized the field, granting access
168 to over a billion georeferenced species occurrence records via platforms like GBIF and BirdLife
169 International (Zizka et al., 2019). However, biodiversity databases often integrate data of
170 varying quality from disparate sources. Metadata, collection methods, and timestamps, is
171 frequently incomplete or inconsistent, which reduce data utility and reliability for research and
172 conservation purposes (Zizka et al., 2019). To address these challenges, ecological
173 cyberinfrastructure must prioritize openness in data, methods, standards, and code (Farley et
174 al., 2018).

175 Evidence synthesis has become essential in integrating and analyzing published data from
176 different sources. Handling spatial data adds another layer of complexity. Differences in
177 Coordinate Reference Systems (CRS) can lead to misinterpretations of latitude and longitude.
178 For example, CRS may vary in coordinate order (Lat/Long vs. Long/Lat) or format (decimal
179 degrees vs. degrees, minutes, and seconds). To avoid these issues, researchers must
180 explicitly document how coordinates are encoded, ensuring clear communication with users
181 (Spatial Data on the Web Best Practices, n.d.).

182 Standardized reporting formats also play a key role in organizing and synthesizing metadata,
183 enhancing data curation, findability, and reuse (Crystal-Ornelas et al., 2022). Therefore, there
184 is a need for a tool that focuses on open, reproducible, and standardized science, facilitating
185 the easier implementation and integration of geospatial data into ecological research.

186

187 OVERVIEW

188 We present `decimatoR`, a new R package for converting various formats of coordinates from
189 published literature to decimal degrees. As a general approach, `decimatoR` identifies the
190 alternative coordinate formats and then performs a set of wrangling actions on latitude and
191 longitude data to convert all of them into decimal degrees. The novelty of this package is that
192 it deals with different formats of reported coordinates: degrees-minutes-seconds (DMS) and
193 degrees-decimal-minutes (DDM). Another novelty is that this package can function not only
194 for single coordinate values, but also for coordinate intervals, which is a common method to
195 report geographic ranges: 12'45"–12'55". This package is useful for spatial data syntheses
196 and meta-analyses, since coordinates can be reported in various formats in literature. The
197 package is implemented in R (R Core Team, 2020) and the source code, vignette and
198 functionalities can be found at <https://github.com/elizavetashch/decimatoR>.

199

200 THE `decimatoR` WORKFLOW

201 This package provides functions designed to process geographic coordinates from published
202 literature into decimal degrees (DD), enabling analysis of datasets containing different
203 coordinate formats.

204 A dataframe in R consists of columns, with each column being a vector. Rows represent
205 observations, and these observations hold values in the columns. However, each observation
206 is created separately, which can lead to inconsistencies. For example, the first observation
207 might be reported in decimal degree format, making its value in the coordinate column
208 numeric. Meanwhile, the second observation could be reported in degrees, minutes, and
209 seconds format, resulting in its value being a character string. When such columns are read
210 into R, the coordinate column becomes a vector of strings. This happens because R forces all
211 values in a column to the same type - so even initially numeric values (e.g., decimal degrees)
212 are converted to character strings.

213 To process such a coordinate column, we must address each string (i.e., each value in the
214 column) individually, while applying a function to the entire vector.

215 This leads to two types of functions in the package:

- 216 • those that work with individual strings (named “`functionaction_string`”, e.g.
217 “`extract_direction_string`”)
- 218 • those that operate on vectors of strings (named “`functionaction_vector`”, e.g.
219 “`extract_direction_vector`”), and therefore include the corresponding
220 `_string` function.

221 A function designed to work with a vector of strings (applied to a column of a dataset) does no
222 more than apply the corresponding `_string` function to each element of the vector. In
223 essence, the core action lies within the `_string` function, while the `_vector` function simply
224 iterates through the vector, applying the `_string` function to each element.

225 There are two exceptions, however, the `process_coordinates_to_dd` and
 226 `identify_coordinate_format`, and those will be described in the following.
 227

function name	input arguments	output
<code>process_coordinates_to_dd</code>	<code>df</code> (dataframe), <code>longitude</code> (longitude column), <code>latitude</code> (latitude column)	df with four new columns: <code>long_coordinate_format</code> (factor), <code>lat_coordinate_format</code> (factor), <code>longitude_decimal</code> (numeric), <code>latitude_decimal</code> (numeric)
<code>identify_coordinate_format</code>	<code>df</code> (dataframe), <code>longitude</code> (longitude column), <code>latitude</code> (latitude column)	df with two new columns: <code>long_coordinate_format</code> (factor), <code>lat_coordinate_format</code> (factor)
<code>_string</code>	string	string
<code>_vector</code>	vector (=column)	vector (=column)

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229

230 Step 0: calling the `process_coordinates_to_dd`

231 The `process_coordinates_to_dd` function is the main function for converting
232 coordinates of various formats into decimal degrees. All the subsequent steps are wrapped
233 within this function to ensure a seamless and structured workflow. Users should only call this
234 function to convert their dataset of coordinates. The user must specify four arguments: `df`
235 (`dataset of coordinates`), `longitude` (`longitude column`), `latitude` (`latitude column`) and `option`
236 (`"first"` or `"second"`), which refers to the preferred method of shortening ddm intervals
237 (`described later`).

238

239 Step 1: Identifying Coordinate Formats

240 The first step involves identifying the coordinate format of the longitude and latitude columns
241 in the dataset using the `identify_coordinate_format` function. This function determines
242 the format based on regular expressions, assigning one of five possible values:

- 243 • DD: Decimal Degrees
- 244 • DMS: Degrees, Minutes, and Seconds
- 245 • DDM: Degrees and Decimal Minutes
- 246 • DDM interval: Intervals of Degrees and Decimal Minutes (e.g., 12'45"-12'55")
- 247 • NA: Unrecognized or invalid coordinates (e.g., values exceeding valid
248 latitude/longitude ranges).

249 The input of the function is the dataset, the longitude and the latitude column. Therefore, it is
250 the only function that can be called outside the `process_coordinates_to_dd` without any
251 necessary adjustments. The output of this function are two new columns
252 (`long_coordinate_format` and `lat_coordinate_format`) that store the identified coordinate format
253 of longitude and latitude respectfully as one of the five factors above. The function ensures
254 accurate format detection, which is critical for subsequent calculations.

255

256 Step 2: Handling DDM Intervals

257 For coordinates in the DDM interval format, the `shorten_ddm_intervals_string` function
258 extracts one boundary of the interval. Users can specify whether to extract the "first" or
259 "second" boundary using the `option` argument. For example, the interval "12'45"–12'55"
260 becomes "12'45" if "first" is selected. This step is essential because the package processes
261 one value per coordinate, and intervals cannot be directly converted to decimal degrees. The
262 shortened coordinates are stored in temporary columns (`longitude_temp` and `latitude_temp`).
263 For other formats, these columns mirror the original longitude and latitude values.

264

265 Step 3: Replacing Non-Digit Characters

266 The next step standardizes the coordinate strings by replacing all non-digit characters (except
267 decimal points) with semicolons (;). This is done using the `replace_nondigits_vector`
268 function, which applies `replace_nondigits_string` to each value in the `longitude_temp`
269 and `latitude_temp` columns. Unnecessary whitespaces are also removed during this process.
270 The resulting strings, stored in columns (`longitudecomma` and `latitudecomma`), contain only
271 digits, semicolons, and decimal points, making it easier to extract coordinate components.

272

273 Step 4: Extracting Coordinate Components

274 The `extract_digits_from_string` function splits a cleaned coordinate string into three
275 strings: degrees, minutes, and seconds, and stores each of them in a separate list of strings.
276 The function works by splitting the input string into three strings based on semicolons (;), which
277 act as delimiters. Each of the three strings corresponds to a potential component of the
278 coordinate (degrees, minutes, or seconds). For every input-string 1) non-digit characters
279 (except for dots) are removed using a regular expression, 2) if fewer than three parts exist in
280 the input-string (e.g., no minutes or seconds), the missing values are replaced with 0 (e.g.

281 coordinates reported in the decimal degree format will get the reported value in the first string,
282 and the “second” and “third” strings will be filled with zero values), 3) the three extracted strings
283 are stored in a list of three lists, with each list containing one named string, namely first
284 (degrees), second (minutes), and third (seconds).

285 The corresponding `extract_digits_from_vector` function applies
286 `extract_digits_from_string` to every element in the column, creating new columns
287 (`longitudedigits` and `latitudedigits`) that store these lists of extracted strings for each coordinate.
288 These lists are then unlisted using the `base::unlist` function to convert the list elements
289 into atomic vectors. Subsequently, the `tidyr::unnest_wider` function is applied to expand
290 the unlisted values into six separate columns: `longitudedigits_first`, `longitudedigits_second`,
291 and `longitudedigits_third` (representing degrees, minutes, and seconds for longitude) and
292 `latitudedigits_first`, `latitudedigits_second`, and `latitudedigits_third` (for latitude). This
293 transformation ensures that each component of the coordinates is stored in its own column for
294 straightforward numerical calculations in the subsequent steps.

295

296 Step 5: Converting to Decimal Degrees

297 Using the extracted components, the package calculates decimal degrees for longitude and
298 latitude using the formula:

$$299 \quad \textit{Decimal Degrees} = \textit{Degrees} + \frac{\textit{Minutes}}{60} + \frac{\textit{Seconds}}{3600}$$

300 The results are decimal numbers, stored in the columns `longitude_DD` and `latitude_DD`.

301

302 Step 6: Extracting Coordinate Direction

303 The `extract_direction_string` function is used to determine the sign of the coordinate
304 string based on whether the initial coordinate string (longitude or latitude) contains directional

305 markers (“Ss” for south, “Ww” for west) or starts with a negative sign (-). This function returns
306 “+” for northern or eastern directions and “-” for southern or western directions.

307 This string-based function is incorporated into its corresponding vectorized function,
308 `extract_direction_vector`, to handle multiple coordinate strings simultaneously in a
309 column. The result is a new column (`longitude_direction` or `latitude_direction`) specifying the
310 directional sign.

311

312 Step 7: Applying the Direction to Coordinate Values

313 The `apply_direction_string` function adjusts the sign of the numeric coordinate
314 values based on the extracted directional component. It takes the absolute value of the
315 coordinate (from the `longitude_DD` or `latitude_DD`) and negates it if the direction is “-” (south
316 or west) (from the `longitude_direction` or `latitude_direction`).

317 The `apply_direction_vector` function applies the `apply_direction_string` function
318 across all pairs of values and directions. The output is the `longitude_decimal` and
319 `latitude_decimal` columns, containing the converted coordinates in decimal degrees and a
320 direction sign.

321

322 Step 8: Cleaning the Output

323 Finally, unnecessary intermediate and temporary columns are removed via `dplyr::select`.
324 The output is the original dataset with added columns for coordinate formats and decimal
325 degrees (`long_coordinate_format`, `lat_coordinate_format`, `longitude_decimal`,
326 `latitude_decimal`).

327

328 USAGE AND DEPENDENCIES

329 4.1. Example of usage

330 The `decimatoR` workflow can be implemented easily using popular R packages (`dplyr`,
331 `purrr`, `tidyr`, `stringr` and `rlang`), as well as the core functions of the package. Here we
332 provide a simple example using a toy dataset. A detailed tutorial of the package is provided at
333 [\[https://github.com/elizavetashch/decimatoR\]](https://github.com/elizavetashch/decimatoR).

334

```
335 # _string function:  
extract_direction_string <- function(coordinate_string) {  
  direction_string <- base::ifelse(stringr::str_detect(coordinate_string, "[SsWw]") |  
  stringr::str_starts(coordinate_string, "^-"), "- ", "+ "  
  )  
  return(direction_string)  
}  
  
# _vector function:  
extract_direction_vector <- function(strings) {  
  direction_strings <- base::lapply(strings, extract_direction_string)  
  return(direction_strings)  
}
```

335

336

337 4.2. Dependencies on other packages

338 The package uses `dplyr` for data manipulation, `tidyr` for reshaping data, `stringr` for string
339 handling, `rlang` for managing programming constructs, and `purrr` for applying functions to
340 lists and vectors. These dependencies ensure efficient and flexible data processing.

341

342 DISCUSSION

343 5.1. Comparison with other R packages

344 Tools like `CoordinateCleaner` (Zizka et al., 2019), `scrubr` (Chamberlain, 2016), `biogeo`
345 (Robertson et al., 2016), and `modestR` (García-Roselló et al., 2013) focus on pre-processing
346 standardized coordinates from online databases, and focus mainly on the CRS conversion.
347 Meanwhile, spatial data packages such as `rgdal` (retired and transitioned to `sf`, `stars`, and
348 `terra`) provide tools for spatial data handling and coordinate transformations, but lack
349 functionalities for identifying and converting coordinate reporting formats. Of all the packages
350 mentioned above, only `biogeo` currently addresses the issue of reporting and converting
351 coordinate formats such as decimal degrees (DD), degrees-minutes-seconds (DMS), and
352 degrees-minutes (DM) through the `dmsparse` function (Robertson et al., 2016). However, this
353 package has not been updated recently and is no longer available on CRAN as of December
354 2024. Moreover, it does not provide tools to identify and report coordinate formats or work with
355 coordinate intervals.

356

357 5.2. Limitations and future developments

358 Although the variation of coordinate formats in literature is considerable, `decimatoR` deals with
359 almost all of them. However, we could only address systematic discrepancies among
360 coordinates. In other words, we could not incorporate solutions for errors or erroneous formats
361 in our code. Human errors are common in literature, but they are not systematic and they have
362 to be dealt individually or be excluded. In addition, the coordinate format depends on the
363 software and hardware used to record the coordinates.

364 Some improvements that can be incorporated in future versions are increasing flexibility by
365 allowing users to apply minor functions outside a dataframe and ensuring the function can
366 handle cases where users want to process only latitude or longitude without the need to
367 process the whole dataset.

368

369 CONCLUSION

370 There is an extensive variety of formats in which spatial data, particularly coordinates, can be
371 represented. These mainly include varying coordinate referencing systems, however varying
372 reporting formats such as decimal degrees, degrees-minutes, degrees-minutes-seconds
373 (dms) and dms-intervals contribute largely to data variability. Therefore it is necessary to have
374 tools that harmonize coordinates across formats and standards to ensure consistency and
375 accuracy in spatial analyses. decimatoR provides a ready-to-use, user-friendly workflow to
376 process varying coordinates formats to the decimal degree format. Although there are
377 packages that have similar functions, the novelty of decimatoR is that only one function has
378 to be applied in order to process the whole dataset, identify coordinate format for each
379 observation, and convert its coordinates to decimal degree format. One further important
380 feature of the decimatoR is the ability to work with coordinate intervals, which was not
381 addressed in previous similar packages. The package reduces research waste, contributes to
382 standardization of research practices and open science. We expect that this package will
383 support scientists who are working on spatial ecology, biodiversity research, environmental
384 monitoring, and other fields that require collection of geospatial data from varying sources,
385 simplifying coordinate handling and eliminating preprocessing challenges.

386

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423 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

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